

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Strain Sensing Capability of Polyaniline-Based Conductive Glass Fibre Reinforced Composite

Sukanta Das and Tomohiro Yokozeki

The University of Tokyo, Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Presentation Plan

Introduction

- Background of the topic
- Basic Concepts
- Summary of previous research
- Motivation of current research

Experimental methodology

Results and discussion

Summary

Introduction : Background

Composites Structure: Replacing Metals

- ✓ High specific strength.
- ✓ Good fatigue strength & corrosion resistance.

Composites Structure: Challenges

- ✓ Structural Health Monitoring.
- ✓ Failed due to lightning strike.

Composites Structure: Available Solutions

- ✓ Strain Gauge: Costly and measure discrete points
- ✓ Metal Mesh: Additional cost & weight gain

There is a need to develop advanced materials, which can act as **‘Multifunctional Structural Material’**.

Introduction : Background

✓ Why polyaniline?

- ✓ Economic
- ✓ Easy to process
- ✓ Environmentally stable

Introduction : Basic Terminologies

❖ How the Polyaniline (PANI) system gets electrical conductivity?

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/app.30460>

<https://cnls.lanl.gov/~rgarcia/Conferences/ICAM/icam/newpage22.htm>

Introduction : Basic Terminologies

❖ How the PANI system different from nano-filler system?

• Nano-Fillers

- Agglomeration (CNTs)
- Percolation thresholds (Metallic)
- Stacking issues (graphene)
- Stress concentration

• PANI-System

- No agglomeration
- No percolation issues
- No stacking
- No stress concentration

Introduction : Summary of previous research

- ✓ Polyaniline-based conductive polymer (PANI System) has been developed.
- ✓ Reported the potentiality of PANI system as a **“Aerospace Structural Material”**.
- ✓ Also reported its capability as a **“Lightning Strike Protection”**.

[1] V. Kumar, T. Yokozeki, T. Goto, T. Takahashi, Mechanical and electrical properties of PANI-based conductive thermosetting composites, *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos.* 34 (2015) 1298–1305.

[2] V. Kumar, T. Yokozeki, T. Goto, T. Takahashi, Synthesis and characterization of PANI-DBSA/DVB composite using roll-milled PANI-DBSA complex, *Polym. (United Kingdom)*. 86 (2016) 129–137.

[3] V. Kumar, T. Yokozeki, T. Goto, T. Takahashi, S.R. Dhakate, B.P. Singh, Irreversible tunability of through-thickness electrical conductivity of polyaniline-based CFRP by de-doping, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 152 (2017) 20–26.

[4] V. Kumar, S. Manomaisantiphap, K. Takahashi, T. Goto, N. Tsushima, T. Takahashi, T. Yokozeki, Cationic scavenging by polyaniline: Boon or bane from synthesis point of view of its nanocomposites, *Polymer (Guildf)*. 149 (2018) 169–177.

Introduction : Motivation of the current work

• Objectives

- ❑ *make use of PANI system as “a multifunctional material.”*
- ❑ “multifunctionality” means,
 - Strain Sensing
 - ✓ Characterize the strain sensor.
 - ✓ **Characterize self-sensing GFRP composites.**
 - Lightning Strike Protection (LSP).
 - ✓ Optimization the PANI system layer.
 - Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) Sheading
 - ✓ Characterize and Optimization the PANI system layer.

Introduction : Characterization of PANI-based matrix

Experiment Setup and Samples

Results : Gauge Factor

$$R = \frac{\rho L}{A} \quad \text{Where, } A = w.t$$

- ✓ Load rate. : 1.0 mm/min
- ✓ Elongation range : 0.6 mm
- ✓ Gauge Factor : ~ 0.71

Results : Incremental Strain Study

Increase Order Strain

- ✓ Load rate : 1.0 mm/min
- ✓ Elongation range : 0-1000N (+200N)

SN	ST	EN	Residual
C1	0	0.00622	0.00622
C2	0.00622	0.01469	0.00846
C3	0.01469	0.02806	0.01337
C4	0.02806	0.04910	0.02104
C5	0.04910	0.08845	0.03936

Results : Strain Rate Study

Strain Rate

Strain rate : 0.1 – 1 mm/min

Load level : 500N

SN	Strain Rate	Slop
1	1.0 mm/min	0.595
2	0.7 mm/min	0.578
3	0.5 mm/min	0.590
4	0.1 mm/min	0.660

Results : Thermal Stability Study

- ✓ **Parameters :**
 - 1) 10 °C/min
 - 2) Heating-Cooling

- ✓ **Observation :**
 - 1) Negligible unrecoverable resistance
 - 2) Unstable

Summary

- ✓ Explain the need of the multifunctional materials.
- ✓ Discuss the properties of the PANI-based conductive polymer matrix.
- ✓ Different characterization studies confirm the self-sensing ability of the PANI based conductive GFRP composite.
- ✓ Thermal stability study confirmed the recoverability of sensor.

Das, Sukanta, Vipin Kumar, and Tomohiro Yokozeki. "Strain sensing behavior of multifunctional polyaniline-based thermoset polymer under static loading conditions." *Polymer Testing* (2019): 105916.

Future Study

- Coated the PANI system layer on GFRPs to measure the mechanical vibration.
- Optimize the PANI system layer on CFRPs for LSP.
- Characterize and Optimize the PANI system layer for EMI shielding on FRPs structures.

N A M A S K A R

THANK YOU FOR LISTENING